

1 **Saponins from edible spears of wild asparagus inhibit AKT,**
2 **p70S6K, and ERK signalling, and induce apoptosis through**
3 **G0/G1 cell cycle arrest in human colon cancer HCT-116 cells**

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16
17 **Abbreviations:** **AKT**, RAC-alpha serine/threonine-protein kinase; **AMC**, 7-
18 amino-4-methylcoumarin; **DMSO**, dimethyl sulfoxide; **dSAP**, digested saponin
19 extract; **ERK**, extracellular signal-regulated kinase; **HT**, Huetor-Tajar; **HTSAP**,
20 Huetor-Tajar asparagus saponin; **IC50**, half maximal inhibitory concentration;
21 **KRAS**, Kirsten rat sarcoma viral oncogene homolog; **MS/MS**, tandem mass
22 spectrometry; **mTOR**, mammalian target of rapamycin; **MTT**,
23 methylthiazolyldiphenyl-tetrazolium bromide; **m/z**, mass to charge ratio;
24 **p70S6K**, S6 kinase; **PARP-1**, poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase 1; **PIK3CA**,
25 phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate 3-kinase, catalytic subunit alpha.

26 **Abstract**

27 The effects of steroidal saponins from edible spears of wild *triguero* Hueter-
28 Tajar asparagus on some of the oncogenic molecular pathways that are
29 affected in human colon cancer cells were investigated. Reverse-phase
30 chromatography and a new HPLC–MS method were used to respectively
31 isolate and analyse the composition of the steroidal saponins. They were
32 resistant to simulated digestion and, when in contact with HTC-116 human
33 colon carcinoma cells, interfered with extracellular signal–regulated kinase
34 (ERK), S6 kinase (p70S6K, mTOR), and RAC-alpha serine/threonine-protein
35 kinase (AKT) pathways by a downregulation of these proteins. The expressions
36 of cyclins D, E, and A were also decreased, leading to G0/G1 cell cycle arrest.
37 In addition, these steroidal saponins induced typical features of apoptosis by the
38 promotion of caspase-3 activity, poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase 1 (PARP-1)
39 cleavage, and DNA fragmentation. These results offer potential dietary
40 intervention strategy against human colon cancer cells.

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42 **Keywords:** Apoptosis, asparagus, cell cycle, colon cancer, human, saponins.

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51 **1. Introduction**

52 Worldwide, there is a growing demand for high-quality, safe, health-promoting
53 or disease-risk reducing foods. Therefore, the nutraceutical and therapeutic
54 potential of dietary bioactive compounds is of increasing interest to both the
55 scientific community and the food industry. Colon cancer represents almost
56 10% of all tumours. It is the third most common cancer in men in developed
57 countries (after lung and prostate cancers) and the second in women (after
58 breast cancer) with approximately 1 million new cases in the world each year.
59 Only 5-10% of these cases are due to genetic factors, while more than 70%
60 have their roots in the diet and other lifestyle factors (van Duijnhoven et al.,
61 2009).

62 Previous studies have shown that saponins, which are naturally occurring
63 compounds widely distributed in a variety of plants, exhibit anticancer activity by
64 inducing cell cycle arrest and apoptosis, and by inhibiting proliferation in
65 numerous types of human cancer cells (Bhardwaj et al., 2014; Liu & Li, 2014;
66 Zhang et al., 2014). Saponins refer to a diverse family of secondary metabolites
67 that contain a sugar moiety glycosidically linked to a hydrophobic aglycone.
68 Legumes, especially soybeans (Omizu, Tsukamoto, Chettri, & Tamang, 2011),
69 chickpeas (Ruiz et al., 1996), leeks (Fattorusso, Lanzotti, Taglialatela-Scafati,
70 Di Rosa, & Ianaro, 2000), onions (Lanzotti, Romano, Lanzuise, Bonanomi, &
71 Scala, 2012), and white asparagus (Lee, Yoo, & Patil, 2010) are the richest
72 dietary source of saponins for humans. We have recently reported that a green
73 wild asparagus (*triguero* Huetor-Tajar, HT, landrace), as a valuable ingredient of
74 the Mediterranean diet, may also provide bioactive phytochemicals in relatively
75 large amounts (Fuentes-Alventosa et al., 2008; Rodriguez et al., 2005) including

76 unusual steroidal saponins (Vazquez-Castilla et al., 2013a). The quantity of
77 steroidal saponins was 10-100 times higher in the spears of *triguero* HT
78 asparagus than those found in green asparagus commercial hybrids (Vazquez-
79 Castilla et al., 2013b). It is noteworthy that chemoprevention of cancer by
80 asparagus saponins is a property commonly explored in non-edible parts of the
81 plant, such as roots (Liu et al., 2009), leaf extracts (Verma, Tripathi, & Das,
82 2014), fruits (Shao et al., 1999), and bottom-stems (Wang, Liu, Zhao, Zhang, &
83 Pang, 2013). However, little is known about the anticancer potential activity of
84 the saponin fraction from edible asparagus spears. Information pertaining to
85 digestive stability of saponins from asparagus spears is also scarce. The aims
86 of this study were to address the stability of saponins from spears of *triguero* HT
87 asparagus during simulated digestion and to evaluate their anticancer effects
88 and underlying mechanisms in human colon cancer HCT-116 cells.

89

90 **2. Materials and Methods**

91 **2.1. Chemicals and reagents**

92 Pepsin (EC 3.4.23.1) from porcine gastric mucosa, α -amylase (EC 3.2.1.1) and
93 pancreatin from porcine pancreas, bile extract porcine, methylthiazolyldiphenyl-
94 tetrazolium bromide (MTT), and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) were purchased
95 from Sigma Chemical Co. (St. Louis, MO, USA). Protodioscin was purchased
96 from Chromadex Chemical Co. (Barcelona, Spain). All cell culture reagents
97 were purchased from Gibco (Madrid, Spain). Hoechst 33342 (H1399) was
98 purchased from Molecular Probes (ThermoFisher Scientific, Madrid, Spain).
99 Poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase 1 (PARP-1) antibody (7D3-6; 551024) was
100 purchased from BD Pharmingen (San Jose, CA, USA), phospho-protein kinase

101 B (AKT, #4051), total-AKT (#2920), phospho-S6 kinase (p70S6, #9205), total-
102 p70S6 (#9202) antibodies were purchased from Cell Signalling (Danvers, MA,
103 USA). Phospho-extracellular signal–regulated kinase (ERK, M8159), total-ERK
104 (M3807), and β -tubulin (T7816) antibodies were purchased from Sigma
105 Chemical Co. Cyclin D (sc-8396), cyclin A (sc-751), and cyclin E (sc-198) were
106 purchased from Santa Cruz Biotechnology (Texas, TX, USA).

107

108 **2.2. Taxonomic identification and authenticity of *triguero* Huetor-Tajar** 109 **asparagus**

110 The *triguero* HT asparagus is also known as “Morado de Huetor” and the only
111 tetraploid asparagus cultivar, together with the Italian “Violetto d’Albenga”, in
112 Europe (Moreno et al., 2006). Previous studies on strain identification and
113 phylogeny have suggested that the *triguero* HT asparagus is close to
114 *Asparagus officinalis* and *A. maritimus* (Moreno et al., 2008a, 2008b). Since
115 2000, the European Commission registered the *triguero* HT asparagus as
116 Protected Geographical Indication in the European Union (European
117 Commission, 2000). Only fresh spears of the *triguero* asparagus harvested from
118 HT landrace, Granada (Spain), were used in the present study.

119

120 **2.3. Preparation of saponin extract**

121 Spears from the *triguero* HT asparagus were extracted with 70% acetone as
122 previously described (Vazquez-Castilla et al., 2013b). Briefly, the extract was
123 loaded onto a column of Amberlite XAD-16 (ratio 170 mL resin/kg of fresh
124 asparagus spears). The column was washed with water followed by 20%, 40%,
125 and 96% of ethanol, using a ratio of 1/4 (v/v) versus the sample loaded. The

126 saponins were eluted with 40% of ethanol.

127

128 **2.4. *In vitro* digestion of saponin extract**

129 The mouth, the stomach, and the small intestine are compartments of the
130 gastrointestinal tract that determine the bioaccessibility of any nutrient, including
131 the saponins. It has been established the composition of digestive solutions that
132 mimic the variety of digestive levels in the human physiology (Boyer, Brown, &
133 Liu, 2005). The detailed components of these digestive solutions are listed in
134 the supplementary material (Table S1). Samples of saponin extract (5 mg) were
135 first homogenized with 10 mL portions of saliva-like solution (including α -
136 amylase) and incubated in a water-bath with agitation for 5 min at 37 °C (mouth-
137 like digestion); the samples were then acidified to pH 2.0 with HCl before the
138 addition of pepsin (200 mg in 5 mL of 0.1 M HCl) and incubated with agitation
139 for 1 h at 37 °C (gastric-like digestion); afterwards, the pH was increased up to
140 5.5-6.0 with 1 M NaHCO₃ and pancreatin (4 mg/mL), and bile extract (25 mg/mL)
141 were added, while the mixture was finally incubated with agitation for 2 h at 37
142 °C (small intestinal-like digestion). Aliquots from five independent replicates
143 were taken at the middle and end of each digestive-like process, rapidly cooled
144 on ice and lyophilized. Controls without digestive enzymes were run in parallel.
145 Only aliquots obtained after the completion of the small intestinal phase of
146 digestion (named digested saponin extract, dSAP) were used for cell culture
147 experiments.

148

149 **2.5. Saponin analysis by HPLC–MS**

150 The identification and quantification of saponins were carried out in extracts

151 subjected or not subjected to *in vitro* digestion applying a HPLC-MS based
152 method (Waters 600; Waters, Milford, MA, USA) fitted with a C-18
153 chromatography reverse-phase column (Mediterranean Sea18, 5- μ m particles,
154 4.4 x 250 mm) supplied by Teknokroma (Barcelona, Spain). Solvents that
155 constituted the mobile phase were acidified aqueous (A) and acidified
156 acetonitrile (B) with 0.1% formic acid. The separation was achieved using
157 gradient elution of 0-30 min, 20% B; 30-60 min, linear gradient to 30% B; 60 to
158 70 min linear gradient to 100% B and 70-80 min, linear gradient 20% B. The
159 flow rate was set at 1 mL/min and the injection volume was 20 μ L. The HPLC
160 was interfaced to a MS quadrupole mass analyser (ZMD4, Waters) via an
161 electrospray ionization (ESI) source operated in positive (capillary voltage at 50
162 eV) and negative (capillary voltage at 50 and 100 eV) modes; the cone voltage
163 and collision energy were set at 3 kV and 12 V, respectively. The source and
164 desolvation temperatures were 120 and 200 $^{\circ}$ C, respectively. The flow rate to
165 the ESI source was decreased up to 200 μ L/min by a splitter.

166

167 **2.6. Cell culture**

168 The human colon adenocarcinoma cell line HCT-116 was obtained from the
169 ATCC (#CCL 247; Bethesda, MD, USA). Cells were grown at 37 $^{\circ}$ C with 5%
170 CO₂ and 90% relative humidity in McCoy's 5A medium supplemented with 10%
171 heat-inactivated foetal bovine serum, 100 U/mL penicillin, and 100 μ g/mL
172 streptomycin.

173

174 **2.7. Cell viability assay**

175 Cell viability was assayed based on the ability of live cells to reduce MTT

176 (Jaramillo et al., 2010). HCT-116 cells were cultured in 96-well plates at a
177 density of 10^4 cells/well in 200 μ L of medium. The cells were grown to 70-80%
178 confluence, and then they were treated with vehicle (DMSO, <0.1%) or dSAP at
179 indicated concentrations for 12, 24, and 48 h before adding the MTT solution for
180 3 h at 37 °C. All MTT assays were carried out in three separate experiments,
181 each one including five replicates. The osmolality of culture media
182 supplemented with DMSO or dSAP was controlled with a Knauer semi-micro
183 osmometer (Knauer and Co., Berlin, Germany).

184

185 **2.8. Western blot analysis**

186 Total cellular proteins, extracted from HCT-116 cells at different experimental
187 conditions, were examined by western blot analysis as previously described
188 (Lopez et al., 2013). Briefly, cells were washed once with PBS and gently lysed
189 in RIPA buffer containing 1 mM Na_3VO_4 , 1 mM NaF, 1 μ g/mL aprotinin, 1 μ g/mL
190 leupeptin, 1 μ g/mL pepstatin, and 1 μ M PMSF at 4 °C with shaking for 30 min.
191 Cell homogenates were then transferred in a 1.5 mL tube and centrifuged 10
192 min, 10000 x g at 4 °C. Total proteins in the supernatant were collected, their
193 concentration determined using the Bradford protein assay and stored at -80 °C.
194 Samples were subjected to SDS-PAGE, Western blot analysis and transferred
195 onto nitrocellulose membrane (0.22 μ m, Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA).
196 Membranes were immunoblotted with mouse anti-phospho-Akt, mouse anti-Akt,
197 mouse anti-phospho-ERK1/2, mouse anti-ERK, mouse anti-PARP-1, rabbit anti-
198 phospho-p70S6K, mouse anti-p70S6K, mouse anti-Cyclin D, rabbit anti-Cyclin
199 A, rabbit anti-Cyclin E, and mouse anti-B-Tubulin 1 antibodies. Specific antigen-
200 antibody complexes were detected with the SuperSignal West Pico

201 Chemiluminescent Substrate (ThermoFisher Scientific, Madrid, Spain). Protein
202 loading equivalence was corrected in relation to the expression of β -tubulin.

203

204 **2.9. Cell cycle analysis**

205 Cell cycle distribution was analysed by flow cytometry as previously described
206 (Jaramillo et al., 2010). Briefly, cells were washed three times with ice-cold PBS.
207 The cell pellet was resuspended in 200 μ L of 70% ice-cold ethanol and 200 μ L
208 of PBS, and stored at -80 °C. For cell cycle analysis, cells were thawed, washed
209 twice with PBS, and suspended in 0.5 mL of staining reagent (50 μ g/mL PI, 50
210 U/mL RNase, 0.1 mM EDTA, 0.1% Triton X-100, PBS). After incubation for 30
211 min at 37 °C in the dark, DNA fluorescence was measured using a Becton
212 Dickinson (BD Biosciences, Madrid, Spain) FACScanto II flow cytometer with an
213 excitation wavelength of 488 nm and emission wavelength of 585 nm. Pulse
214 width area signals were used to discriminate between G2 cells and cell doublets.
215 Data were analysed using FlowJo v5.7.2 software (Tree Star, Ashland, OR,
216 USA). Approximately 10000 events per sample were analysed, and the relative
217 distribution of cells in each phase (G0/G1, S, and G2/M) was displayed as
218 histograms.

219

220 **2.10. DNA condensation and fragmentation assays**

221 Apoptosis was also determined by DNA condensation assay using Hoechst
222 33342 dye as previously described (Lopez et al., 2013). In addition, low-
223 molecular-weight genomic DNA was evaluated following a previous method with
224 some modifications (de Mello et al., 2015). Briefly, all the cells (including floating
225 cells) were harvested and washed twice with PBS. Cells were treated with a

226 lysis buffer (50 mM Tris, 10 mM EDTA, 0.5% sodium sarkosinate, 0.5 mg/mL
227 RNAase A) for 1 h at 37 °C, before the addition of 1 mg/mL proteinase K and an
228 additional incubation for 3 h at 56 °C. DNA was isolated by the phenol-
229 chloroform-isoamyl alcohol method and dissolved in TE buffer (pH 7.4). A
230 volume of the resulting solution containing 2 mg of DNA was loaded on 1.8%
231 agarose gel. The isolated DNA was visualised by ethidium bromide staining
232 under a UV lamp.

233

234 **2.11. Caspase-3 activity assay**

235 Caspase-3 activity was determined using a caspase-3 assay kit, Fluorimetric
236 (CASP3F, Sigma-Aldrich) as previously described (Lopez et al., 2013). The
237 cells were incubated with the substrate, acetyl Asp-Glu-Val-Asp 7-amino-4-
238 methylcoumarin, and the fluorescence intensity of the resulting 7-amino-4-
239 methylcoumarin (AMC) product was recorded at wavelengths of 360 and 460
240 nm for excitation and emission, respectively.

241

242 **2.12. Statistical analysis**

243 Data were analysed using IBM[®] SPSS[®] statistics v23.0 for Windows (IBM,
244 Madrid, Spain). All quantitative data are represented as mean ± SD from
245 triplicate experiments performed in parallel unless otherwise indicated. Mean
246 values among treatment groups were compared by the ANOVA followed by
247 Duncan's multiple comparison test. A level of $p < 0.05$ was accepted as
248 statistically significant.

249

250 **3. Results**

251 **3.1. Characterization of saponins in extracts from edible spears of**
252 ***triguero* Hueter-Tajar asparagus**

253 The amount of saponins quantified in fresh wild asparagus was 4.6 mg/100 g of
254 fresh spear. There were five major peaks of *triguero* HT asparagus saponins
255 (HTSAP): HTSAP-1, HTSAP-2, HTSAP-12, HTSAP-6, and HTSAP-8 (Figs. 1A-
256 1B). The tandem mass (MS/MS) spectrum showed that all of these saponins
257 are derived from a furostan-type steroidal genin with a single bond between C5-
258 C6 of the B ring; they have been described in previous reports (Vazquez-
259 Castilla et al., 2013a, 2013b). The most abundant saponins HTSAP-1, HTSAP-
260 12, and HTSAP-6 represented more than 90% of the total saponin content from
261 edible spears of *triguero* HT asparagus (Table 1).

262

263 **3.2. Steroidal saponins from edible spears of *triguero* Hueter-Tajar**
264 **asparagus are stable to a simulated digestion**

265 The exposure of steroidal saponins to sequential incubations with oral-, gastric-,
266 and small intestinal-like fluids did not substantially affect their stability.

267 Representative chromatograms of steroidal saponins in fractions from edible

268 spears of *triguero* HT asparagus following different phases of simulated

269 digestion are shown in the supplementary material (Figure S1). All of the

270 steroidal saponins remained stable with a final recovery range of 87.5-94.2%

271 (Table 2). Similar stability was observed for samples of steroidal saponin

272 extracts subjected to fluids with salts but without enzymes (data not shown).

273

274 **3.3. Steroidal saponins from edible spears of *triguero* Hueter-Tajar**
275 **asparagus are cytotoxic to human colon cancer HCT-116 cells**

276 Aliquots of saponin extracts obtained after the completion of simulated oral,
277 gastric, and small intestinal digestion (dSAP) were used for successive
278 experiments. HCT-116 cells were treated with different concentrations (0-250
279 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) of dSAP for 12, 24, and 48 h. dSAP was cytotoxic in a dose- and time-
280 dependent manner ($p < 0.05$, Fig. 2). The concentration producing a 50% of cell
281 death (IC₅₀) of dSAP on HCT-116 cells was $\sim 193 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for 24 h and ~ 76
282 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for 48 h. No further decrease in cell viability was detected at
283 concentrations of dSAP above 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$.

284

285 **3.4. Steroidal saponins from edible spears of *triguero* Hueter-Tajar**
286 **asparagus inhibit the phosphorylation of AKT, p70S6K, and ERK in human**
287 **colon cancer HCT-116 cells**

288 We performed the expression of AKT, p70S6K, and ERK by western blot in
289 HCT-116 cells treated with dSAP at IC₅₀ concentration for 48 h. The dSAP
290 decreased the expression of these cell survival proteins in HCT-116 cells ($p <$
291 0.05 , Figs. 3A-3D).

292

293 **3.5. Steroidal saponins from edible spears of *triguero* Hueter-Tajar**
294 **asparagus induce caspase-3 activity, PARP-1 cleavage, and DNA**
295 **fragmentation in human colon cancer HCT-116 cells**

296 Caspase-3 activity was significantly increased ($p < 0.05$) in HCT-116 cells
297 treated with dSAP at IC₅₀ concentration for 48 h (Fig. 4A). As expected, PARP-
298 1 cleavage occurred in HCT-116 cells treated with dSAP (Figs. 4B-4C). After
299 cellular DNA content analysis, we observed that dSAP induced apoptosis and
300 DNA fragmentation ($p < 0.05$) of HCT-116 cells by means of hypodiploid DNA

301 content in the sub-G0/G1 cell population (Fig. 4D). These effects of dSAP on
302 HCT-116 cells were confirmed by a characteristic DNA-ladder during DNA gel
303 electrophoresis (Fig. 5A) and by pyknotic nuclei under fluorescence microscopy
304 (Figs. 5B-5E).

305

306 **3.6. Steroidal saponins from edible spears of *triguero* Hueter-Tajar** 307 **asparagus induce cell cycle arrest by reducing the expression of cyclins** 308 **D, A, and E in human colon cancer HCT-116 cells**

309 We determined the cell cycle distribution in HCT-116 cells treated with dSAP at
310 IC50 concentration for 48 h. The dSAP increased the number of HCT-116 cells
311 in sub-G0/G1 and arrested HCT-116 cells in G0/G1 phase at the expense of
312 those in G2/M phase ($p < 0.05$, Figs. 6A-6B). The western blot analysis of
313 cyclins D, A, and E confirmed that dSAP decreased the expression of these
314 cell-cycle stimulating proteins in HCT-116 cells ($p < 0.05$, Figs. 6C-6F).

315

316 **4. Discussion**

317 In this study, we have applied a new HPLC–MS method (Vazquez-Castilla et al.,
318 2013b) to analyse the composition of saponins in the spears of *triguero* HT
319 asparagus. This edible part of the plant was found to provide high amounts of
320 furostanol steroidal saponins that differ from protodioscin, which is the most
321 abundant of asparagus steroidal saponins (up to 85% of the total saponin
322 concentration in white asparagus spears) (Fuentes-Alventosa et al., 2009; Lee,
323 Yoo, & Patil, 2010). While protodioscin has a double bond between carbons 5
324 and 6 of the B ring in the six-ringed C₂₇ skeleton, steroidal saponins from the
325 spears of *triguero* HT asparagus have a single bond between C5 and C6. We

326 identified three major saponins derived from a furostan-type steroidal genin
327 (HTSAP-1, 6, and 12) accounted for 90% of total saponins in the spears of
328 *triguero* HT asparagus. Steroidal saponins from non-edible parts of asparagus
329 (*A. racemosus*, *A. filicinus*, *A. officinalis* L., *A. oligoclonos*) have been reported
330 to exhibit important pharmacological activities, including immunomodulation
331 (Gautam et al., 2009; Pise, Rudra, & Upadhyay, 2015) and cytotoxicity (Bhutani,
332 Paul, Fayad, & Linder, 2010; Kim et al., 2005; Liu et al., 2009; Wu et al., 2010;
333 Zhou et al., 2007) on several human tumour cells. To our knowledge, this is the
334 first report focused on anticancer effects of steroidal saponins from spears as
335 an edible part of asparagus, which in this case is an autochthonous green
336 asparagus variety of the type *triguero* from the south of Spain (HT landrace,
337 Granada) (Vazquez-Castilla et al., 2013a). It is worth mentioning that the
338 absorption of ingested saponins is very low (Liu et al., 2013; Okawara,
339 Tokudome, Todo, Sugibayashi, & Hashimoto, 2014) and the stability of steroidal
340 saponins to digestive processes is not fully understood; yet this is the first study
341 addressing the stability of asparagus steroidal saponins during simulated oral,
342 gastric, and small intestinal digestion. Steroidal saponins from the spears of
343 *triguero* HT asparagus remained stable with greater than 90% recovery of initial
344 amounts. Previous studies also reported a high stability of steroidal saponins in
345 tea from ginseng root extracts by similar procedures of simulated digestion (Kim
346 et al., 2014; Kim, Lee, Shin, Son, & Kim, 2009). Our observations on digestive
347 resistance of steroidal saponins from the spears of *triguero* HT asparagus,
348 together with the well-known low bioavailability of saponins, may suggest that
349 these steroidal saponins remain in the gastrointestinal tract and are colon-
350 accessible, where they may exert their biological effects. Thus, we observed an

351 inhibition of cell growth when human colon cancer HCT-116 cells were in
352 contact with the artificial digest of steroidal saponins from the spears of *triguero*
353 HT asparagus. Apart from protodioscin (Hu & Yao, 2002), our data are the first
354 to demonstrate the cytotoxic activity of furostanol saponins from (an edible part
355 of) asparagus on human colon cancer cells. Previous studies were mainly
356 focused on cytotoxicity of spirostane-type steroidal saponins from non-edible
357 parts of the asparagus (Bhutani et al., 2010; Kim et al., 2005; Liu et al., 2009;
358 Wu et al., 2010; Zhou et al., 2007). Importantly, furostanol saponins have been
359 shown to be less toxic for normal cells than spirostanol saponins (Lee et al.,
360 2010).

361 Colonic epithelial cell line HCT-116 is considered a tissue culture model
362 of apoptosis resistance in human colon cancer, in which genes Kirsten rat
363 sarcoma viral oncogene homolog (KRAS, G13D) and phosphatidylinositol-4,5-
364 bisphosphate 3-kinase, catalytic subunit alpha (PIK3CA, H1047R) are
365 constitutively activated (Ahmed et al., 2013). Both oncogenes are downstream
366 effectors of ERK, AKT, and mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR) signalling
367 pathways that promote cell growth, survival, and the transition from colon
368 adenoma to carcinoma (Grady & Pritchard, 2014). Recent approaches to KRAS
369 and PIK3CA mutant tumour treatment with ERK (Lamba et al., 2014) and
370 PI3K/AKT/mTOR (Janku et al., 2013) inhibitors have stressed the need to
371 expand resources available to suppress redundant signalling networks for
372 cancer treatment. We found that steroidal saponins from the spears of *triguero*
373 HT asparagus decreased the phosphorylated forms of ERK, AKT, and p70S6K
374 (as a marker of mTOR activation) in HCT-116 cells. These findings in HCT-116
375 cells are in contrast to the increased phosphorylation of ERK by oleanane-type

376 triterpenic saponins from aerial parts of *Glochidion eriocarpum* (Nhiem et al.,
377 2012), but are similar to the effects on AKT and mTOR phosphorylation by total
378 saponins from the roots of *Radix astragali* (Law, Auyeung, Chan, & Ko, 2012).
379 The steroidal saponin Aspaflioside B from the roots of *A. filicinus* has been
380 reported to increase the phosphorylation of ERK in human HepG2
381 (hepatocellular carcinoma) cells (Liu et al., 2015). Other non-asparagus
382 steroidal saponins have been shown to decrease the phosphorylation of ERK
383 and AKT in human HL-60 (promyelocytic leukemia), PC-3 (prostate cancer),
384 SNU-C5 (colorectal cancer), MCF-7 (breast cancer), MAD-231 (breast cancer),
385 and MCF Her2 (breast cancer) cells (Srinivasan et al., 2009; Thao et al., 2014).
386 Recent studies have also reported that the phosphorylation of protein kinases
387 p38 and JNK, mainly involved in apoptosis (Sui et al., 2014), are increased by
388 the dammarane-type triterpenic saponin Jujuboside B from *Zizyphus jujuba* in
389 HCT-116 cells and human gastric cancer AGS cells (Xu, Lee, Kang, & Kim,
390 2014). Therefore, the simultaneous suppression of ERK, AKT, and mTOR
391 signalling may be, at least in part, a possible mechanism by which steroidal
392 saponins from the spears of *triguero* HT asparagus induce a loss of viability in
393 HCT-116 cells. These observations underscore the selective efficacy of these
394 steroidal saponins of interfering any complementary and/or feedback interplay
395 between RAS/RAF/MEK/ERK and PI3K/AKT/mTOR pathways (Gao, Shi, Xia,
396 Inagaki, & Tang, 2015). It is tempting to speculate that the amphiphilic character
397 of saponins could disturb the process of receptor tyrosine kinase activation at
398 the cytoplasmic membrane level (Lorent, Quetin-Leclercq, Mingeot-Leclercq,
399 2014), not excluding the possibility of dSAP inhibiting the receptor tyrosine
400 kinase domain (Sathishkumar et al., 2013). We further observed the entry of

401 cells in apoptosis by several means: enhancement of sub-G0/G1 cells,
402 caspase-3 activation, PARP-1 cleavage, and DNA fragmentation. In addition,
403 cyclins D, E, and A were downregulated and cells were arrested at G0/G1
404 phase of the cell cycle. Similar effects have been reported for non-asparagus
405 triterpenoid saponins in decreasing cyclin D expression and promoting cell cycle
406 arrest in the G0/G1 phase, accompanied by an inhibition of cell proliferation
407 and/or induction of apoptosis in HCT-116 cells (Du et al., 2012; Du et al., 2013;
408 Lee et al., 2015; Li et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2015). Cyclin D is a pivotal
409 regulator of G0/G1 transition in cell cycle (Jayaraman & Jamil, 2014) and its
410 downregulation or inhibition has been previously attributed to STAT-dependent
411 mechanisms (Podolak, Galanty, & Sobolewska, 2010) or docking of bioactive
412 molecules into the active site of cyclins (Yang et al., 2015). It is likely that the
413 mechanisms involved in cell cycle modulation for G0/G1 arrest to induce
414 apoptosis are highly conserved in the hystotype of human colon cancer cells,
415 since asparagus steroidal saponins such as Asparanin A from the roots of *A.*
416 *officinalis* (Liu et al., 2009) and Aspafilioside B from the roots of *A. filicinus* (Liu
417 et al., 2015) exhibit cytotoxic effects by affecting a different profile expression of
418 cyclins and increasing caspase-3 activation and PARP cleavage, though
419 arresting the cell cycle at the G2/M phase in human HepG2 (hepatocellular
420 carcinoma) cells. We did not observe direct effects of dSAP on lysis in HCT-116
421 cells, which is in line with the low potency of steroidal saponins to induce
422 membrane destabilization with cytoskeleton integrity disassembly when
423 compared to triterpene saponins (Podolak, Galanty, & Sobolewska, 2010).

424

425 **5. Conclusions**

426 In summary, our study suggests that steroidal saponins from edible spears of
427 *triguero* HT asparagus are stable to simulated digestion. These saponins, when
428 in contact with human colon cancer HCT-116 cells, block ERK, AKT, and p70S6
429 (mTOR) signalling pathways; arrest the cell cycle at G0/G1 phase by interfering
430 the expression of cyclins D, E, and A; and induce cell death through the
431 apoptotic pathway via caspase-3, leading to PARP-1 cleavage and DNA
432 fragmentation. The potential relevance of these steroidal saponins on other
433 human cancer cell types to translate into cancer care warrants further research.

434

435 **Conflict of interest**

436 The authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

437

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443

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689

690 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

691 **Fig. 1.** Mass spectrometric analysis of the steroidal saponin extract from edible
692 spears of *triguero* HT asparagus. 1: HT asparagus saponin (HTSAP)-1; 2:
693 HTSAP-2; 3: HTSAP-12, 4: HTSAP-6; 5: HTSAP-8 (A). Negative electrospray
694 ionization-MS spectra of the HTSAP-12 saponin (B). m/z, mass to charge ratio.
695

696 **Fig. 2.** Loss of cell viability of HCT-116 cells treated with digested saponin
697 extract (dSAP, 0-250 µg/mL) for 12, 24, and 48 h. Each point represents the
698 mean ± SD (n = 5). Two-way ANOVA analysis: Time effect: $p < 0.0001$; Dose
699 effect: $p < 0.0001$; and Time x Dose: $p < 0.0001$. *Statistical differences
700 between 24 and 48 h ($p < 0.05$). † Statistical differences between 12 and 24 h
701 ($p < 0.05$).

702
703 **Fig. 3.** Western blot analysis of total and phosphorylated form of AKT (A and B),
704 p70S6K (A and C), ERK (A and D), and β-tubulin (protein loading control) of
705 HCT-116 cells treated with digested saponin extract (dSAP, 76 µg/mL) for 48 h.
706 Untreated cells are referred as control. Each point represents the mean ± SD (n
707 = 3). *Statistical differences compared to control ($p < 0.05$).

708
709 **Fig. 4.** Caspase-3 activity (A), western blot of PARP-1 (B), quantification of
710 PARP-1 cleavage (C), and sub-G0/G1 analysis (D) of HCT-116 cells treated
711 with digested saponin extract (dSAP, 76 µg/mL) for 48 h. Untreated cells are
712 referred as control. Each point represents the mean ± SD (n = 3). *Statistical
713 differences compared to control ($p < 0.05$). AMC, 7-amino-4-methylcoumarin.

714

715 **Fig. 5.** Gel agarose electrophoresis (A) of DNA from HCT-116 cells treated with
716 digested saponin extract (dSAP, 76 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) for 48 h (lane 2). DNA from
717 untreated cells is shown in lane 1. Phase contrast (B and D) and hoescht 33342
718 staining (C and E) of HCT-116 cells treated with dSAP (76 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Arrows
719 indicate pyknotic nuclei.

720

721 **Fig. 6.** Cell cycle profile (A), cell cycle quantification (B), and western blot
722 analysis of cyclin D, A, and E (C-F) in HCT-116 cells treated with digested
723 saponin extract (dSAP, 76 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) for 48 h. Untreated cells are referred as
724 control. Each point represents the mean \pm SD (n = 3). *Statistical differences
725 compared to control ($p < 0.05$).

Table 1. Saponin profile in edible spears of *triguero* HT asparagus.

Saponin	Rt (min)	Mw (Da)	mg/100 g FW
HTSAP-1	25.56	1052	1.25 ± 0.14
HTSAP-2	26.58	920	0.17 ± 0.03
HTSAP-12	31.08	1050	1.49 ± 0.13
HTSAP-6	32.01	1036	1.55 ± 0.16
HTSAP-8	33.40	904	0.14 ± 0.04

HT, Huetor-Tajar; HTSAP1-12, HT asparagus saponins; Rt, retention time; Mw, molecular weight; FW, fresh weight.

Table 2. Stability of saponins from edible spears of *triguero* HT asparagus during the *in vitro* digestion assay. Each saponin has been quantified (in $\mu\text{g/mL}$) at the end of each step of the model. The percentage of the original amount of each saponin is shown between parentheses.

Saponin	m/z (MS/MS)	Original	Mouth-like digestion	Gastric-like digestion	Small intestinal-like digestion	Total loss (%)
HTSAP-1	1051	198 \pm 14	178 \pm 7 (89.9%)	180 \pm 8 (90.9%)	176 \pm 8 (88.8%)	11.2%
HTSAP-2	919	28 \pm 2	25 \pm 1 (89.3%)	24 \pm 1 (85.7%)	25 \pm 1 (89.3%)	10.7%
HTSAP-12	1049	241 \pm 13	222 \pm 9 (92.1%)	226 \pm 13 (93.8%)	227 \pm 9 (94.2%)	5.8%
HTSAP-6	1035	250 \pm 16	228 \pm 10 (91.2%)	228 \pm 10 (91.2%)	229 \pm 9 (91.6%)	8.4%
HTSAP-8	903	24 \pm 1	22 \pm 1 (91.6%)	22 \pm 1 (91.6%)	21 \pm 1 (87.5%)	12.5%

HT, Huetor-Tajar; HTSAP1-12, HT asparagus saponins; MS/MS, tandem mass spectrometry; m/z, mass to charge ratio.

Fig. 1

A

B

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Supplementary Material

Saponins from edible spears of wild asparagus inhibit AKT, p70S6K, and ERK signalling, and induce apoptosis through G0/G1 cell cycle arrest in human colon cancer cells

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Table S1. Solutions of the *in vitro* digestion assay.

	Saliva-like solution	Gastric-like solution	Small intestinal-like solution (duodenum + bile)
Chemical reagents	2 mL NaCl 1.6 g/L 2 mL KCl 0.2 g/L 2 mL NaH ₂ PO ₄ 0.3 g/L 2 mL KH ₂ PO ₄ 0.05 g/L 0.2 mL CaCl ₂ 0.14 g/L 0.2 mL MgSO ₄ 1.23 g/L 0.2 mL NaHCO ₃ 2.01 g/L	2 mL NaCl 8.17 g/L 2 mL KCl 0.37 g/L	12 mL NaHCO ₃ 0.5 mL HCl 3.6 g/L
Enzymes	0.1 mL α -amylase 1 mg/mL	0.2 mL pepsin 40 g/L	0.5 mL pancreatin 4 g/L 0.5 mL bile 25 g/L
pH	6.8	2.0	8.0

Fig. S1. Chromatograms of steroidal saponins in fractions from edible pears of *triguero* HT asparagus following different phases of simulated digestion. Relative absorbance of the native (red line), gastric digested (green line), and intestine digested (blue line) extracts showing the main peaks corresponding to the steroidal saponins. All lines started at the same level of relative absorbance, however, for the sake of clarity the distinct lines have been moved along the Y-axis.